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The mycoherbicide *Fusarium oxysporum* strain FT2 is a pathogen of *Orobanche ramosa*, a destructive parasitic weed of vegetables in Mediterranean countries. FT2 produces metabolites with antifungal activity, which may hamper its use in combination with other fungal biocontrol agents. The inhibitory effect of the organic extract of FT2 cultures was assayed towards the antagonistic strain *Trichoderma barzianum* CFA16, resulting in 82% inhibition of CFA16 colonies grown on PDA supplemented with 5% of FT2 extract. In order to improve the resistance of CFA16 to antifungal compounds of FT2 and ameliorate the compatibility between the two biocontrol agents, a UV-mutagenesis strategy was adopted. Conidia of CFA16 were exposed to UV-C rays for 120 seconds to obtain 80-85% of kill. Then, an aliquot of the irradiated suspension was seeded on water agar supplemented with FT2 extract. After 24 h, germinated conidia were isolated as presumptive tolerant mutants and transferred on PDA + 5% FT2 extract. The colony growth of mutants was measured daily and compared with that of the wild type (wt). 200 presumptive UV-C mutants were isolated and 25 mutants that exhibited up to 75% faster growth than the wt in the presence of 120 ppm of an FT2 antifungal metabolite were selected for further studies of biocontrol efficacy and ecological fitness. The development of strains with enhanced tolerance to toxic metabolites is expected to lead to an improvement of compatibility of CFA16 and biocontrol *F. oxysporum* strains, as well as to an increase of competitive capability of CFA16 towards phytopathogenic *F. oxysporum* strains.

SANITARY SELECTION OF SWEET CHERRY. A. Materazzi, H. Bouyahia and E. Triolo. Dipartimento di Coltivazione e Difesa delle Specie Legnose "G. Scaramuzzi", Sezione di Patologia Vegetale, Università degli Studi, Via del Borghetto 80, 56124 Pisa, Italy. E-mail: amatazzi@agr.unipi.it

The research project "Tutela e valorizzazione della ciliegia di Lari", supported by the "Fondazione Cassa di Risparmio di Pisa", was launched for preserving the genetic resources of sweet cherry (*Prunus avium*) in Lari (Pisa, Italy). A multidisciplinary team was established and 12 autochthonous sweet cherry cultivars in danger of extinction were identified. The research was carried out on 99 thirty-year-old plants, distributed in 10 orchards. Composite samples of 15 leaves from each plant were collected in spring and tested by ELISA and RT-PCR for the presence of the following viruses: Plum pox virus (PPV), *Prunus necrotic ringspot virus* (PNRSV), *Prune dwarf virus* (PDV), *Cherry leaf roll virus* (CLRV), *Apple mosaic virus* (ApMV) and *Apple chlorotic leaf spot virus* (ACLSV). Laboratory tests showed that 76 of 99 plants (76.8%) were infected by at least one virus. The most frequent virus was PDV, accounting 98.7% of the infections (75 of 76 infected samples); PNRSV was detected in 2 samples and only in one case ACLSV was detected in mixed infection with PDV. PPV, CLRV and ApMV were not found. A subsequent analysis, showed that the sour cherry (*P. cerasus*) rootstock mother plants, largely used in the area as a source seeds for seedlings, was 100% infected by PDV. As reported, PDV is transmitted to seeds with about 70% efficiency, so we can conclude that the high incidence of this virus (75.8%) can be mainly attributed to the use of infected rootstocks.

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF PLUM BARK NECROSIS STEM PITTING-ASSOCIATED VIRUS BY IC-PCR AND ELISA

DURING DIFFERENT SEASONS OF THE YEAR. S. Matic, M. Morelli and D. Boscia. Dipartimento di Protezione delle Piante e Microbiologia Applicata, Università degli Studi and Istituto di Virologia Vegetale del CNR, Sezione di Bari, Via Amendola 165/A, 70126, Bari, Italy. E-mail: d.boscia@ba.iva.cnr.it

Plum bark necrosis stem pitting-associated virus (PBNSPaV) was monitored during different seasons over the year by the comparative use of ELISA and immuno-capture (IC)-PCR. A field-grown tree of Japanese plum cv. Black Beaut, inoculated with an Italian PBNSPaV isolate (ASP), was sampled, testing 18 leaf samples in spring, summer and autumn and cortical tissues from dormant branches in winter. Virus was detectable during all seasons using both techniques. The highest virus detection was found in spring by both techniques (100%). During summer and autumn, IC-PCR was more successful in virus detection (100%), than ELISA which gave positive reactions with 83% and 56% of the samples, respectively. During winter, ELISA detected more samples (94%), compared to IC-PCR (89%). The virus was rather uniformly distributed in the tree canopy since it was detected in the apical, middle and basal part of the branches with slight differences. Taking into account the estimated infection values on the whole, both techniques gave satisfactory detection levels, for PBNSPaV was detected in 97% of the samples by IC-PCR and in 83% of the samples by ELISA. The use of both detection assays seems to afford an efficient identification of PBNSPaV the whole year round.

WATERMELON MOSAIC VIRUS: THE PREDOMINANT VIRUS INFECTING WINTER MELON IN SOUTHERN ITALY. M. Meneghini¹, C. Mennone², M.L. Palermo³, G.F. Siddu⁴ and L. Tomassoli¹. ¹CRA, Istituto Sperimentale per la Patologia Vegetale, Via C.G. Bertero 22, 00156 Roma, Italy. ²ALSIA, Regione Basilicata, Strada Statale Jonica 106, km 448,2, 75010 Metaponto (MT), Italy. ³Regione Sicilia Assessorato Agricoltura e Foreste, U.O. 107, Via Toniolo 44b, 91026 Mazara del Vallo (TP), Italy. ⁴Sardegna Agricoltura LAORE, Via Giovanni XXIII 99, 09096 Santa Giusta (OR), Italy. E-mail: l.tomassoli@ispave.it

In Italy, *Watermelon mosaic virus* (WMV, genus *Potyvirus*, family *Potyviriidae*) has been known since 1973 and it is one of the most common viruses affecting cucurbits in open-air crops together with *Zucchini yellow mosaic virus* (ZYMV) and *Cucumber mosaic virus* (CMV). However, WMV has been long considered a minor pathogen because it induces very mild symptoms on the leaves and it seldom affects yield and quality of the fruits. In the last years, extensive outbreaks of a severe mosaic were observed on field-grown winter melons (*Cucumis melo* L. var. *inodorus*) in Southern Italy. Infected plants showed mosaic, vein-banding and malformation of the leaves and discolorations of the fruits which heavily reduced market quality. Samples from several infected fields in Sicily, Basilicata and Sardinia, the main producing regions of this crop, were analyzed by DAS-ELISA using commercial antisera against the most frequent mosaic-inducing viruses of cucurbits, mainly belonging to the genus *Potyvirus*. Two years of assays showed the WMV is the prevalent causal agent of mosaic of winter melon (infection rates: WMV, 75%; CMV, 15%; other viruses, 10%). WMV thus represents a real threat in those regions where winter melon is of major economic importance. In comparison with other cucurbit potyviruses, WMV occurs on a wide host range including species of other families and many weeds growing all year round. In addition several aphids species are vectors of this virus. Thus, it is necessary to implement appropriate sanitary measures, as insecticide treatments, culture practices, or providing resistant varieties to control WMV.